

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ
JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

ДАВРИЙЛИГИ: 2016-2025

ЖИЛД 10
СОҢ 5

2025

ЧОП
ЭТИЛГАН САНА:
06.11.2025

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

10 ЖИЛД, 5 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 10, НОМЕР 5

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 10, ISSUE 5

Бош мухаррир:

Ризаев Жасур Алимжанович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети ректори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Ўзбекистон Республикаси
Фанлар академиясининг Иммунология ва инсон
геномикаси институти директор ўринбосари,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Масъул котиб:

Самиева Гулноза Утқуровна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Нашр учун масъул:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
онкология кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

ТАХРИРИЯТ КЕНГАШИ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

*Иммунология ва инсон геномикаси институти директори –
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Ўзбекистон
Республикаси Фанлар академияси академиги*

Jin Young Choi

*Сеул миллий университети Стоматология мактаби оғиз ва
юз-жағ жарроҳлиги департаменти профессори, Жанубий
Кореянинг юз-жағ ва эстетик жарроҳлик ассоциацияси
президенти*

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети проректори, 1-клиникаси бош
врачи. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети Гистология, цитология ва
эмбриология кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

*тиббиёт фандар доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети болалар жарроҳлиги кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент тиббиёт
академияси Оилавий тиббиётда акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси профессори ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Очилов Улугбек Усмонович

*DSc, доцент, СамДТУ Дипломдан кейинги таълим
факултети Психиатрия курси мудири. СамДТУ Илмий
кенгаши котиби. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Шавази Наргиз Нуралiena

*DSc. Доцент, СамДМУ 3-сон акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси мудири <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Юлдашев Равшан Захидович

*Тоҷикистон Давлат тиббиёт университети Онкология
ва нур таъхис кафедраси мудири, Тиббиёт фанлари
доктори, Профессор. Душанбе, Тоҷикистон.
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Саидов Сандамир Абборович

*тиббиёт фанлар доктори,
Тошкент фармацевтика институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Бабалджанов Ойбек Абдуҷаббарович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент педиатрия
тиббиёт институти, Тери-таносил, болалар тери-таносил
касаликлари ва ОИТС кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Тошкент
педиатрия тиббиёт институти Факультет болалар
хирургия кафедраси. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327*

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
№2-сон Педиатрия, неонатология ва болалар
касаликлари пропедевтикаси кафедраси доценти.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
Тошкент давлат стоматология институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети, онкология кафедраси профессори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Даминов Феруз Асадуллаевич

*Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
2-сон Даволаш факультети декани,
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент.
Самарқанд, Ўзбекистон.*

Миржурев Элбек Миршавкатович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
ЎзССВ Тиббий ходимларни касбий малакасини
ривожлантириши марказининг Нейрореабилитация
кафедраси мудири, Тошкент, Ўзбекистон*

Тагаев Шерқабул Бойқабдулович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, хирургия кафедраси
доценти Тошкент давлат стоматология институти.
ORCID: 0009-0004-7661-9253.*

Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналлов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Главный редактор:

Ризаев Жасур Алимджанович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ректор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5468-9403

Заместитель главного редактора:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
доктор медицинских наук, Заместитель директора Института иммунологии и геномики человека Академии наук Республики Узбекистан, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-3933

Ответственный секретарь:

Самиева Гульноза Уткуровна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, доцент кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-0888-9150

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна
директор Института иммунологии и геномики человека доктор медицинских наук, профессор, академик АН РУз

Jin Young Choi
профессор департамента оральной и челюстно-лицевой хирургии школы стоматологии Стоматологического госпиталя Сеульского национального университета, Президент Корейского общества челюстно-лицевой и эстетической хирургии

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, проректор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, заведующий кафедрой Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-0615-0144

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович
доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Детской хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2650-4445

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна
Доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины Ташкентской медицинской академии **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9313-4918

Очилов Улугбек Усманович
DSc, доцент, заведующий курсом психиатрии факультета постдипломного образования СамГМУ. Секретарь Ученого совета СамГМУ. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Шавази Наргиз Нуралиевна
DSc, доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии N 3 СамГМУ. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>

Юлдашев Рашид Захидович
Заведующий кафедрой Онкологии и лучевой диагностики Таджикского медицинского университета, д.м.н., профессор, Душанбе, Таджикистан <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>

Сандов Сандамир Аброрович
доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский фармацевтический институт **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-6616-5428

Бабаджанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович
доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский педиатрический медицинский институт, доцент кафедры Дерматовенерология, детская дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович
доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской детской хирургии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович
доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии, неонатологии и перепеленки детских болезней №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергатовна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5272-5503

Даминов Феруз Асадуллаевич
Декан лечебного факультета №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, доктор медицинских наук, доцент. Самарканд, Узбекистан.

Мирджураев Эльбек Миршавкатович
Заведующий кафедрой Нейрореабилитации Центра развития профессиональной квалификации медицинских работников МЗ РУз, д.м.н., профессор Ташкент, Узбекистан

Тагаев Шеркабул Бойкабулович
доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры хирургии, Ташкентский государственный стоматологический институт. **ORCID:** 0009-0004-7661-9253.

Верстка: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Chief Editor:

Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich
MD, DSc, Professor of Dental Medicine,
Rector of the Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Deputy Chief Editor:

Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdievich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Deputy Director of the Institute
of Immunology and Human Genomics of the Academy of
Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Responsible secretary:

Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna
doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Responsible for publication:

Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shavkatovna
PhD, Docent Department of Oncology
Samarkand State medical university
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Aripova Tamara Uktamovna

*Director of the Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics -
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Academician of the
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Jin Young Choi

*Professor Department of Oral and Maxillofacial
Surgery School of Dentistry Dental Hospital
Seoul National University, President of the
Korean Society of Maxillofacial Aesthetic Surgery*

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmatovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Vice-Rector
Samarkand State Medical University, Chief Physician of
the 1st Clinic ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Oripov Firdavs Suratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Head of the Department of Histology, Cytology and
Embryology of Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Mavlyanov Farkhod Shavkatovich

*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
Surgery, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Magzumova Nargiza Makhamovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department
of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Family Medicine, Tashkent
Medical Academy. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich

*DSc, Docent, Head of the Psychiatry Course at the Faculty of
Postgraduate Education of SamSMU. Secretary of the Academic
Council of SamSMU. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Shavazi Nargiz Nuraliyena

*DSc, Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Obstetrics
and Gynecology N 3 of Samarkand State Medical University.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Yuldashev Ravshan Zakhidovich

*Head of the Department of Oncology and Radiation Diagnostics
at Tajik State Medical University, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor. Dushanbe, Tajikistan <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Saidov Saidamir

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Babadjanov Oybek Abdujabbarovich

*Doctor of sciences in medicine, Tashkent Pediatric
Medical Institute, Docent the Department of
Dermatovenerology, pediatric dermatovenerology
and AIDS, ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
Faculty of Children Department of Surgery.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

Yuldashev Botir Akhmatovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
Pediatrics, Neonatology and Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ibragimova Malika Xudayberganovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxammatkulovich

*DSc, Professor of Oncology,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Daminov Feruz Asadullaevich

*Dean of the Faculty of Medicine No. 2, Samarkand State
Medical University, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate
Professor. Samarkand, Uzbekistan.*

Mirjuraev Elbek Mirshavkatovich

*Head of the Department of Neurorehabilitation Center
for the development of professional qualification of
medical workers, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor. Tashkent, Uzbekistan
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2111-4388>*

Tagaev Sher Kabul Baykabulovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor
of Surgery Department, Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID: 0009-0004-7661-9253.*

Page Maker: Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

DENTISTRY AND OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY WITH MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

1. **Ahmedov Alibek Bahodirovich, Olimov Siddiq Sharifovich**
DENTAL REHABILITATION MEASURES FOR PATIENTS WITH FATTY
HEPATOSIS.....11
2. **Alimova Dono Mirjamolovna, Mustagizova Feruza Abduraximovna**
THE ROLE OF PERIODONTAL DISEASE IN CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE.....18
3. **Amonov Shavkat Ergashevich, Bezbakh Dmitry Ilyich, Amonov Aminjon Shavkatovich**
LARYNGEAL PAPILOMATOSIS: A REVIEW OF MODERN METHODS OF
DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT.....25
4. **Nuraliyev Nekkadam Abdullayevich, Razikova Dilnoza Kadyrovna**
INDICATIONS OF IMMUNE SYSTEM HUMORAL IMMUNE FACTORS IN RELAPSING
HERPETIC STOMATITIS IN CHILDREN.....31
5. **Eshimova Parvina Behzod qizi, Alimova Dono Mirjamalovna, Suleymenov Askar
Nurlanovich**
A MODERN PERSPECTIVE ON LOCAL TREATMENT OF RECURRENT APHTHOUS
STOMATITIS.....36
6. **Kuryazov Shoxrux Akbarovich**
METHODS OF EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF ORAL ORGAN PATHOLOGIES IN GIRLS
DURING PUBERTY.....41
7. **Suleymenov Askar Nurlanovich, Alimova Dono Mirjamalovna, Eshimova Parvina
Behzod qizi**
COMPARISON OF THE CLINICAL AND RADIOLOGICAL EFFICACY OF EPOXY
SILERS OF TRADITIONAL COMPOSITION AND WITH ADDITIVES OF
QUATERNARY AMMONIUM.....50

ONCOLOGY

8. **Djanklich Sayde Mustafayevna, Tillyashaykhov Mirzagaleb Nigmatovich, Imamov
Olim Abdilhodjayevich, Berkinov Alisher Aliyevich, Ismailova Umida Abdullayevna**
PREVALENCE OF CERVICAL CANCER IN UZBEKISTAN: INCIDENCE AND
MORTALITY.....56
9. **Iskandarova Shakhnoza Tulkinovna, Khakimova Laylo Nuraliyevna, Yusupov Anvar
Sobirovich**
SPECIFIC FEATURES OF ORGANIZING THE ANESTHESIOLOGY SERVICE IN AN
ONCOLOGICAL CLINIC DURING MAJOR UPPER ABDOMINAL SURGERY.....66
10. **Islamov Khurshid Jamshidovich**
ANALYSIS OF TREATMENT RESULTS FOR PATIENTS WITH RECTAL METASTIC
CANCER.....75
11. **Malikov Muzaffar Abduvakhobovich**
DEVELOPMENT OF A DIAGNOSTIC AND TREATMENT ALGORITHM FOR
DIFFERENTIATED THYROID CANCER BASED ON THE APPLICATION OF
MOLECULAR-GENETIC ANALYSIS METHODS.....83
12. **Sapura Ibragimova, Klevleeva Albina, Babakhanova Nargiza, Rizayeva Feruza,
Erimbetova Indira, Nigmatov Khamidhon, Aripova Nazokat**
OUTCOMES OF BLINATUMOMAB THE INITIAL PHASE OF CHEMOTHERAPY IN
CHILDREN WITH B-CELL ALL.....91
13. **Raximov Nodir Maxammatkulovich, Shaxanova Shaxnoza Shavkatovna, Assatulaev
Akmal Farxadovich, Khakimov Alisher Abduraxmonovich**
COMPREHENSIVE RISK ASSESSMENT OF THROMBOCYTOPENIA IN ONCOLOGY
PATIENTS: FROM PREDICTORS TO PERSONALIZED THERAPY.....97

14. **Mirrakhimova Nargiza Mirzakhidovna, Khikmatullaeva Aziza Saydullaevna, Ibadullaeva Nargiza Saypievna, Abdukadirova Muazzam Aliyevna, Rakhimov Ruslan Ravshanovich**
THE ROLE OF HBV RNA IN THE EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF HBV-ASSOCIATED HEPATOCELLULAR CARCINOMA.....107
15. **Tillyashayxov Mirzagaleb Nigmatovich, Malikov Muzaffar Abduvakhobovich**
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF COMBINED TREATMENT OF DIFFERENTIATED THYROID CANCER.....112
16. **Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shavkatovna, Madaminova Sevarakhon Mukhammadjon kizi, Esankulova Bustonoy Sobirovna, Kamalova Barno Zafarovna**
MODERN CONCEPTS OF PATHOGENESIS AND MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF HPV-ASSOCIATED LESIONS OF THE VULVA AND CERVIX.....119

HEALTHCARE

17. **Israilova Gulida Maratovna, Tuxtarov Baxrom Eshnazarovich, Kodirov Dilmurod Alimxon O'g'li**
METHODS FOR ENHANCING THE TECHNOLOGY OF FORTIFYING FUNCTIONAL MEAT PRODUCTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....124
18. **Nasirova Rano Rakhimovna**
ELECTRONIC MEDICAL RECORDS IN MILITARY MEDICINE: MODERN CAPABILITIES AND IMPLEMENTATION PROSPECTS.....132

INTERNAL DISEASES

19. **Aripdjanova Shakhlo Sardarovna, Zufarov Pulat Saatovich, Baykhanova Dilrabo Jamalitdinovna, Ashurova Munisa Jalalitinovna**
USE OF ADAPTOGENS IN THE COMPLEX THERAPY OF PATIENTS WITH CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES.....142
20. **Mamasoliyev Nematjon Soliyevich, Nishonova Nodiraxon Akramovna, Botirov Jaxongir Akramjon Ug'li**
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT AND CHANGE OF PRENOSOLOGICAL RISK FACTORS OF ARTERIAL HYPOTENSION IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE ANDIJAN REGION (PROMISING ANALYSIS OF THE STUDY).....146
21. **Mamasoliyev Nematjon Soliyevich, Nishonova Nodiraxon Akramovna, Botirov Jaxongir Akramjon Ug'li**
LONG-TERM FEATURES OF THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF AGE-RELATED FACTORS OF SMOKING, ALCOHOL CONSUMPTION, AND HYPERCHOLESTEROLEMIA IN THE VALLEY, DEPENDING ON THE PREMORBID PREVENTION OF ARTERIAL HYPOTENSION.....152
22. **Zufarov Pulat Saatovich, Aripdjanova Shakhlo Sardarovna, Baikhanova Dilrabo Jamalitdinovna, Ashurova Munisa Jalalitinovna**
USE OF ADAPTOGENS IN THE COMPLEX THERAPY OF PATIENTS WITH CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES.....157

PEDIATRIC SURGERY AND PEDIATRICS

23. **Ibragimov Qurbonmurod Niyozovich, Akhmedov Yusufjon Maxmudovich**
EVALUATION OF THE RESULTS OF POSTOPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS IN THE SCROTAL FORM OF HYPOSPADIAS IN CHILDREN.....162

24. **Hasanov Aziz Batir O'g'li, Yusupov Shuxrat Abduqosim O'g'li**
MORPHOLOGICAL AND MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF BONE TISSUE IN ALLOXAN-INDUCED OSTEOPATHY AND ITS CORRECTION.....167
25. **Muxamedjanova Fatima Rustamovna**
COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF ANTHROPOMETRIC AND SOMATIC INDICATORS IN CHILDREN PLAYING CHESS AND STUDYING ACCORDING TO THE GENERAL EDUCATION PROGRAM.....173
26. **Muxamedjanova Fatima Rustamovna**
FEATURES OF THE PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN WHO PLAY CHESS.....181
27. **Rakhmatullaev Akmal Abadbekovich, Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich, Abdullaev Kuddus Eshkurbanovich**
CURRENT ISSUES OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF PRIMARY OBSTRUCTIVE MEGAURETER IN CHILDREN.....186
28. **Kurbonov Djafar Djurakulovich, Azizov Mamatkul Kurbanovich, Khurramov Farrukh Mukhsinovich**
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TREATMENT OUTCOMES FOR VARIOUS FORMS OF ACUTE ABDOMINAL PATHOLOGY IN CHILDREN.....197

MORPHOLOGY

29. **Ruziev Sherzod Ibadullayevich., Ismailova Mexriban Olimbayevna**
FORENSIC SIGNIFICANCE OF VASCULAR PLEXUS AND VENTRICULAR MORPHOLOGY IN TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURIES.....207
30. **Ruziev Sherzod Ibadullayevich., Ismailova Mexriban Olimbayevna**
METHODS OF STUDYING THE VASCULAR PLEXUS AND VENTRICULAR SYSTEM IN TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURIES.....215
31. **Sapaeva Sharofat Aminovna**
MORPHOSTRUCTURAL CHANGES IN LUNG TISSUE IN AN EXPERIMENTAL MODEL OF SURFACTANT DEFICIENCY.....221
32. **Ulugbekova Gulrukh Juraevna, Adkhamov Shokhjakhon Abdullajon Ugli**
AGE- AND GENDER-SPECIFIC MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN CRANIOMETRICAL INDICATORS OF THE HEAD AND CRANIAL INDEX IN CHILDREN OF EARLY SCHOOL AGE.....228

NEUROLOGY AND PSYCHIATRY

33. **Adambaev Zufar Ibragimovich, Kilichev Ibodulla Abdullaevich, Saparbaev Kudrat Ismailovich**
TREATMENT OF ISCHEMIC STROKE: FOCUS ON NEUROREGENERATION - MODERN STRATEGIES AND PROSPECTS.....233
34. **Dusov Abdimurod Kholmurodovich, Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich, Dusov Tursunmurad Kholmurodovich**
COMPREHENSIVE ASSESSMENT OF DELAYED HELP-SEEKING FOR PSYCHIATRIC CARE: AN ANALYSIS BASED ON AN INDEXING METHOD.....245
35. **Dusov Abdimurod Kholmurodovich, Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich, Dusov Tursunmurad Kholmurodovich**
FORMS AND SEVERITY LEVELS OF EMOTIONAL-VOLITIONAL DEFICIT IN PARANOID SCHIZOPHRENIA AND THEIR CLINICAL-DYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS.....252

36. **Ismailov Zakhidjon, Mirdjuraev Elbek**
DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT AND COMPREHENSIVE REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN WITH DISEASES OF THE PERIPHERAL NERVOUS SYSTEM.....262
37. **Ismailov Zakhidjon, Mirdjuraev Elbek**
RESULTS OF COMPREHENSIVE REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN WITH DISEASES OF THE PERIPHERAL NERVOUS SYSTEM.....275
38. **Madjidova Yakuthon Nabiyevna, Ergasheva Nargiza Nasriddinovna, Hasanova Nafisa Okilovna**
ASSESSMENT OF THE FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE MUSCULOSKELETAL SYSTEM IN CHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY.....284
39. **Mirdjuraev Elbek, Ismailov Zakhidjon**
OPTIMIZATION OF REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN WITH DISEASES OF THE NEUROMOTOR SYSTEM.....290
40. **Mirjurayev Elbek Mirshavkatovich, Adambayev Zufar Ibragimovich, Samiyev Asliddin Sayitovich, Ergashev G'ulom Bo'riyevich**
REHABILITATION OF NON-SPECIFIC BACK PAIN CAUSED BY MODIC SPONDYLODISCITIS: A RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED TRIAL.....299
41. **Ruzmetova Saodat Umarjonovna**
PERINATAL INVOLVEMENT OF CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM AND ITS IMPACT ON CHILD DEVELOPMENT.....306
42. **Samiyev Asliddin Sayitovich, Bobomurodov Gayrat Allamurodovich, Khushvaktov Nizom Zoirovich, Samiyev Bobur Asliddinovich**
EFFECTIVENESS OF COMPLEX TREATMENT FOR PATIENTS WITH MYASTHENIC CRISIS.....312

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

43. **Axtamov A'zam, Axtamov Azim**
STUDYING THE RESULTS OF RECONSTRUCTIVE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF COMBINED MENISCLE WOUNDS.....316
44. **Axtamov A'zam, Axtamov Azim**
EXPERIENCE IN TREATING INTRA-ARTICULAR FRACTURES OF THE DISTAL PART OF THE HUMERUS IN CHILDREN.....321
45. **Axtamov Azim, Axtamov A'zam**
DIAGNOSIS AND MODERN METHODS OF TREATMENT OF ACETABULUM INJURIES (LITERATURE REVIEW).....325
46. **Urinbayev Payzilla Urinbayevich, Eranov Sherzod Nuraliyevich**
REHABILITATION OF PATIENTS WITH ELBOW JOINT CONTRACTURE IN IMPROPERLY UNIONED SUPRACONDYL FRACTURES OF THE HUMERUS.....332
47. **Zolotova Natalya Nikolaevna**
THE MAIN DIAGNOSTIC AND TREATMENT CRITERIA FOR HIP DISPLASIA IN CHILDREN.....341

SURGERY

48. **Davlatov Salim Sulaymonovich, Khamidov Obid Abdurakhmanovich, Nurmurzayev Zafar Narbayevich**
COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE AND TRADITIONAL BILIARY DECOMPRESSION METHODS IN THE COMPREHENSIVE TREATMENT OF BENIGN MECHANICAL JAUNDICE.....344

49. **Eshkabilov Shukurali Davlatmuratovich, Ixtiyorov Talat Vaxobovich**
ENDOSCOPIC BALLOON DILATION OF ANASTOMOTIC STRICTURES AFTER
SURGICAL REPAIR OF ESOPHAGEAL ATRESIA.....355
50. **Khashimov Rustam Uktamjanovich, Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich, Rakhmanov Kosim
Erdanovich.**
CLINICAL EFFICACY OF MODIFIED AND ENDOVIDEOSURGICAL METHODS IN
HERNIOPLASTY OF INGUINAL HERNIAS.....361
51. **Matlubov Mansur Muratovich, Yusupov Jasur Tolibovich, Khamdamova Eleanora
Gafarovna, Khamdamov Olim Dilmurodovich**
THE ROLE OF ULINASTATIN IN COMPREHENSIVE THERAPY FOR THE
PREVENTION OF POSTOPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS IN CORONARY ARTERY
BYPASS GRAFTING.....371
52. **Rakhimov Oybek Umarovich, Khamdamov Bakhtiyor Zarifovich, Dadayev Shirin
Amanovich**
PERSONALIZED ALGORITHM FOR IMMUNOCORRECTION IN PATIENTS WITH
GENERALIZED PERITONITIS AND HIGH IMMUNOLOGICAL RISK.....378
53. **Togayev Sherkobul Baykobulovich, Baymakov Sayfiddin Risbaevich, Hasanov Bobur
Abduganievich, Ashurov Abdurashid Abdullaevich**
METHODS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF CROHN'S DISEASE OF THE
SMALL AND LARGE INTESTINE.....385

ENDOCRINOLOGY

54. **Alieva Anna Valerovna, Salikhova Zebo Abdulzokhid Kizi, Ismoilova Nazokat
Egamberdi Kizi, Nazarova Bakhora Uktamovna**
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF WOLFRAM AND ALSTROM SYNDROMES.....390
55. **Alidjanova Durдона Abdullajonovna**
DISORDERS OF MENTAL ACTIVITY IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS WITH
TYPE 1 DIABETES.....397
56. **Alikhanova Nodira Mirshavkatovna, Isamukhamedova Istiora Sandjarovna,
Abboskhugaeva Lola Saydganiodgaevna**
GLYCEMIC INDEX AND GLYCEMIC LOAD OF FOOD PRODUCTS FOR CLINICAL
PURPOSES IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES.....408
57. **Akhmedjanova Saodat Fakhadovna**
FUNCTIONAL HYPOTHALAMIC AMENORRHEA: CURRENT INSIGHTS INTO
PATHOGENESIS, DIAGNOSIS, AND THERAPY.....419

OPHTHALMOLOGY

58. **Islamov Ziyovuddin Sadriddinovich, Khamroyeva Yulduz Abdurashidovna, Azimov
Abdullo Asliddin Ugli**
DIAGNOSTIC VALUE OF ELASTOSONOGRAPHY IN CHOROIDAL TUMORS.....423
59. **Myakushkina Ruslana Rashidovna, Yusupov Azamat Farkhadovich, Karimova
Muyassar Khamitovna, Muxanov Shavkat Abduvaliyevich, Gelmanova Tatyana
Ivanovna**
CHANGES IN ABERRATIONS AND THEIR IMPACT ON VISION AFTER LASIK....429
60. **Tosphulatova Arofat Ziyavutdinovna, Khamraeva Yuvalla-Makhliyo Ulmasalievna**
ORTHOKERATOLOGY LENSES IN THE CONTROL OF MYOPIA PROGRESSION IN
CHILDREN (REVIEW ARTICLE).....434
61. **Turakulova Dilfuza Mukhitdinovna, Nazirova Zulfiya Rustamovna, Yunusova Komila
Bakhodirovna**
THE ROLE OF TONOGRAPHIC INDICATORS OF THE EYE IN THE CARE OF
CHILDREN WITH CONGENITAL GLAUCOMA.....443

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

ISMAILOV Zakhidjon
MIRDJURAEV Elbek

Center for the development of professional qualification of medical workers, Tashkent

DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT AND COMPREHENSIVE REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN WITH DISEASES OF THE PERIPHERAL NERVOUS SYSTEM

For citation: Ismailov Zakhidjon, Mirdjuraev Elbek. Diagnosis, treatment and comprehensive rehabilitation of children with diseases of the peripheral nervous system // Journal of Biomedicine and practice. - 2025, vol. 10, issue 5.

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17554268>

ABSTRACT

Objective: The research was carried out to improve the criteria for rehabilitation including drug Ipigrix of sick children with limited movement as a result of damage to the neuromotor system. **Methods:** All patients underwent clinical-neurological, anthropometric and electrophysiological examination. Clinical research methods included analysis of patient complaints, life and disease Anamnesis, general and neurological conditions. The complaints analysis provided information on the intensity, nature and degree of localization of the pain syndrome, the side of the lesion, the degree of movement restriction, the factors that cause or aggravate the pain syndrome, changes in muscle strength and sensitivity. Clinical and neurological examination aimed at detecting sensitivity, movement, reflex and trophic disorders in patients was carried out according to universally established methods. **Results:** After rehabilitation measures with the use drug Ipigrix we noted that in almost all children the condition of the ankle has become normal. After all the rehabilitation (course of rehabilitation for 45 days), the pre-treatment scoliosis of children decreased, 90% of children returned to normal, indicating the high effectiveness of the rehabilitation. After extensive rehabilitation in the main group, there was a decrease in movement restrictions in BDS by 6.6 times, an increase in muscle strength in the legs by 3.5 times, a decrease in response reactions to functional tests by 11.5 times, as well as a recovery in clinical and neurological indicators. Changes in reflexes, muscle strength and sensitivity in the legs were not observed. **Conclusion:** An objective examination revealed different levels of muscle tension in the legs, positive reactions to functional tests and restrictions on active movements. In patients in the comparison group after treatment, the average acute pain decreased, persistent pain and periodic pain decreased.

Key words: Ashner test, Kerdo index, comparison group, muscle hypotrophy, physical rehabilitation, tremors, hypesthesia, dysesthesia, Phallena test

ИСМАИЛОВ Захиджон
МИРЖУРАЕВ Эльбек

Центр развития профессиональной квалификации
медицинских работников, Ташкент, Узбекистан

ДИАГНОСТИКА, ЛЕЧЕНИЕ И КОМПЛЕКСНАЯ РЕАБИЛИТАЦИЯ ДЕТЕЙ С ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯМИ ПЕРИФЕРИЧЕСКОЙ НЕРВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Цель исследования: Исследование было проведено с целью совершенствования критериев реабилитации, включающей применение препарата Ипигрикс, у детей с ограничением двигательной активности вследствие поражения нейромоторной системы. **Методы:** Все пациенты прошли клинико-неврологическое, антропометрическое и электрофизиологическое обследование. Клинические методы исследования включали анализ жалоб пациентов, анамнеза жизни и заболевания, общего и неврологического статуса. Анализ жалоб позволил получить информацию об интенсивности, характере и степени локализации болевого синдрома, стороне поражения, степени ограничения движений, факторах, вызывающих или усугубляющих болевой синдром, изменениях мышечной силы и чувствительности. Клинико-неврологическое обследование, направленное на выявление нарушений чувствительности, движений, рефлексов и трофических расстройств у пациентов, проводилось согласно общепринятым методикам. **Результаты:** После проведения реабилитационных мероприятий с применением препарата Ипигрикс было отмечено, что практически у всех детей состояние голеностопного сустава нормализовалось. После завершения полного курса реабилитации (продолжительностью 45 дней) выраженность сколиоза у детей уменьшилась, у 90% детей наблюдалась нормализация состояния, что свидетельствует о высокой эффективности реабилитационных мероприятий. После проведения комплексной реабилитации в основной группе отмечено уменьшение ограничения движений в нижних конечностях в 6,6 раза, увеличение мышечной силы в ногах в 3,5 раза, снижение реактивных реакций на функциональные пробы в 11,5 раза, а также восстановление клинико-неврологических показателей. Изменений рефлексов, мышечной силы и чувствительности в нижних конечностях не наблюдалось. **Заключение:** При объективном обследовании выявлены различные уровни мышечного напряжения в нижних конечностях, положительные реакции на функциональные пробы и ограничения активных движений. У пациентов группы сравнения после лечения отмечено снижение средней интенсивности острой боли, уменьшение постоянной и периодической боли.

Ключевые слова: проба Ашнера, индекс Кердо, группа сравнения, мышечная гипотрофия, физическая реабилитация, тремор, гипестезия, дизестезия, проба Фаллена

ИСМОЙЛОВ Заҳиджон
МИРЖҶҶРАЕВ Элбек

Тиббиёт ходимларининг касбий малакасини ривожлантириш маркази, Тошкент

ПЕРИФЕРИК НЕРВ ТИЗИМИ КАСАЛЛИКЛАРИ БИЛАН ОҒРИГАН БОЛАЛАРНИ ТАШХИСЛАШ, ДАВОЛАШ ВА КОМПЛЕКС РЕАБИЛИТАЦИЯ ҚИЛИШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Тадқиқот мақсади: Тадқиқот нейромотор тизим зарарланиши натижасида ҳаракат чекланиши бўлган болаларни Ипигрикс препаратини қўллаган ҳолда реабилитация қилиш мезонларини такомиллаштириш мақсадида амалга оширилди. **Усуллар:** Барча беморлар клиник-неврологик, антропометрик ва электрофизиологик текширувдан ўтказилди. Клиник тадқиқот усуллари беморларнинг шикоятлари, ҳаёт ва касаллик анамнези, умумий ва неврологик ҳолатини таҳлил қилишни ўз ичига олди. Шикоятларни таҳлил қилиш оғриқ синдромининг интенсивлиги, характери ва локализация даражаси, зарарланиш томони, ҳаракат чекланиши даражаси, оғриқ синдромини келтириб чиқарувчи ёки кучайтирувчи омиллар, мушак кучи ва сезувчанликдаги ўзгаришлар ҳақида маълумот берди. Беморларда сезувчанлик, ҳаракат, рефлекс ва трофик бузилишларни аниқлашга қаратилган клиник-неврологик текширув умумқабул қилинган усуллар бўйича амалга оширилди. **Натижалар:**

Ипигрикс препаратини қўллаган ҳолда реабилитация тадбирлари ўтказилгандан кейин деярли барча болаларда тобиқ бўғими ҳолати меъёрга келгани қайд этилди. Тўлиқ реабилитация курси (45 кунлик реабилитация курси) тугагандан кейин болаларда даволашгача бўлган сколиоз камайди, 90% болаларда ҳолат меъёрга қайтди, бу реабилитациянинг юқори самарадорлигидан далолат беради. Асосий гуруҳда кенг қамровли реабилитациядан кейин қуйи оёқларда ҳаракат чекланишининг 6,6 марта камайиши, оёқлардаги мушак кучининг 3,5 марта ошиши, функционал синамаларга реактив реакцияларнинг 11,5 марта камайиши, шунингдек клиник-неврологик кўрсаткичларнинг тикланиши кузатилди. Оёқлардаги рефлекслар, мушак куч ва сезувчанликда ўзгаришлар кузатилмади. **Хулоса:** Объектив текширувда оёқларда мушак тарангликнинг турли даражалари, функционал синамаларга ижобий реакциялар ва фаол ҳаракатларнинг чекланиши аниқланди. Даволашдан кейин таққослаш гуруҳидаги беморларда ўртача ўткир оғриқ камайди, доимий ва даврий оғриқ камайди.

Калит сўзлар: Ашнер синамаси, Кердо индекси, таққослаш гуруҳи, мушак гипотрофияси, жисмоний реабилитация, тремор, гипестезия, дизестезия, Фаллен синамаси

1. Introduction

In a clinical neurological examination, patients complained of wheezing - paresthesia, loss of cartilage in the legs, pain in the direction of the affected nerve. Complaints in younger children were reported to consist of loss of cartilage (53.1%) and in the heel area of the ankle (42.2%), pain in the legs (31.5%). Children aged 7-11 years had a significant decline in the number of above complaints between 41.6% and 32.8% respectively with ($p= 0.05$), pain from the affected leg nerve accounting for -23.4%. In the age group of the last Category "11-18 years", complaints decreased to 26.2% - 34.5%, less than the previous indicator, while the increase in pathology does not correspond to age. Thus, the fact that children's complain of pain in the palm of the foot is correlated with the disease, and the loss of cartilage is accompanied by the appearance of hypesthesia in the ham [2]. With increasing age, the number of complaints in girls about pain in the affected leg and the spine, as well as hypesthesia and dysesthesia in the leg, maximized. Among the main indicators, body mass indices (BMI) were evaluated. The average BMI for boys was 26.5 (minimum 17.1, maximum 41.6, standard deviation 4.2), for girls 27.2 (minimum 17.1, maximum 38.7, standard deviation 4.5). Unlike boys, the incidence of postinjective mononeuropathies in girls was lower (6 times higher than in boys) and higher in the older age group (1.8 times higher than in boys). At the same time, in the middle age group (ages 7-11), it was noted that the prevalence among girls is much lower than among boys (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Major neurological complaints in accordance with gender

2. Patients and Methods

2. 1. Patients

One hundred children with damage to the peripheral nervous system from 3 to 18 years old were taken, who were being treated in the Department of neurology rehabilitation of the Republican

Center for the rehabilitation of diseases of the musculoskeletal system. The duration of treatment in the center was on average between 45 and 50 days. Of the 100 children studied, 80 are children with neuropathy that appears after the use of anti-inflammatory nonsteroidal drugs (injections), ten are children with neuropathy that arises from long-term use of orthopedic items, ten are sick children with neuropathy of various etiologies of origin.

2. 2. Treatment methods

The diagnosis of nerve damage was carried out in the following way: stimulation of the nerve was carried out when measuring the rate of impulse conduction in the nerves of movement, but with the subsonic values of the current values.

The evaluation of nerve function was carried out according to the following indicators: delay along the sensory and motor fibers, amplitude and pulse transmission rate the amplitude of the response obtained in v was measured from the top of the negative peak to the zero range the speed of the electrical impulse in m/sec was estimated between the proximal and distal points [3, 4]. The method of studying motion fibers consists in stimulating the motor parts of the peripheral nerves (areas closest to the skin surface) with quadruple pulses 0. 05-0. 5 mc long with a bipolar stimulating electrode away from the cathode to the anode (antidromic electro stimulation method) [5].

3. Results

To improve the diagnostic algorithm, we examined a child with 100 different mononeuropathies between the ages of 3 and 18. From 100 children studied, 80 are children with post-use neuropathy of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (injections), 10 are healthy children who arise from overuse of orthopedic ligaments, 10 are sick children with neuropathy of various etiologies [6]. All children were divided into 2 groups: the main group and the control group. The primary age group of 3-7 consisted of 26 children, 7-11 years old – 20 children, 11-18 years old – 18 children, 15 children in the control group of children under 3-7 years old, 7-11 years old – 13, 11-18 years old-8 children.

As the main complaints, numbness in the legs, hypesthesia, dysesthesia, pain in the direction of the affected nerve of the legs were received. In the younger age group, there were low complaints of hypesthesia (3.1%) and pain in the calf area (9.2%). Among boys, there was a significant increase (36%) between children aged 7-11 in the above complaints of 29.0% and 29.5%, and between children who complained of pain in the leg ($r < 0.05$), and a reliability factor was confirmed ($r < 0.05$). In this case, children aged 7-11 years are a statistically significant risk factor for the development of pathology of the peripheral nervous system (relative risk 3,2-9,4). The most common neurological complaints among children occurred mainly at the age of 11-17 years. The relative risk (by first group indicators) was from 4.0 to 12.8 (Table 1).

Table 1. The main neurological complaints encountered when examined with age

Age	Hypesthesia, %		Pain caused by improper injection (Antibiotics.), %	
	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls
3-7 years	3,1	17,6	9,2	23,5
7-11 years	29,0	16,1	29,5	32,3
11-17 years	39,8	28,6	36,8	44,2
Avarage	29,5	30,9	31,3	40,9

Thus, the prevalence of complaints from young children is directly related to the age of hypesthesia in patients with the usual performed injection technique: with age, complaints increase

in boys. It should be noted that there was found to be a direct correlation between the prevalence of complaints from improperly performed injection among girls, but was not statistically significant [7, 8]. With an increase in the age of the child, the number of complaints about pain in the joints of the legs, as well as hypesthesia in the legs, went back (Table 2).

Table 2.

Results of clinical and neurological examination of children.

Clinical indications	Results	Neuropathy of the legs,%	P
Right leg tumors	Not available	100	<0,01
	There is a breakdown	0	
Left leg tumors	Not available	97,7	<0,07
	There is a breakdown	2. 3	
Right-sided discriminatory intuition	Not available	72,1	
	There is a breakdown	27,9	<0,05
Left-sided discriminatory intuition	Not available	53,5	
	There is a breakdown	46,5	<0,001
Rubbing on the right leg	Not available	97,7	
	There is a breakdown	2,3	<0,001
Rubbing on the left leg	Not available	100	

According to the main group data using developed rehabilitation complexes, the following changes occurred: movement disorders of children up to $85.6 \pm 3.4\%$ decreased moderately ($p \leq 0.05$); the ability to climb the first and second floors of stairs increased by $25.7 \pm 6.0\%$, without the use of additional support (barrier, belt) in the main group ($p \leq 0.05$); $68.3 \pm 3.8\%$, was noted to be $21.8 \pm 4.5\%$ in the control group. In the main group, a statistically significant improvement was achieved in the form of pain reduction of $73.2 \pm 6.4\%$ ($p \leq 0.05$), and dependence on relatives decreased from $45.4 \pm 3.7\%$ to $4.2 \pm 1.6\%$ ($p \leq 0.05$).

According to neurological examination data, statistically significant results were achieved: leg tremors stopped in $57.3 \pm 4.0\%$ of children ($p \leq 0.05$); The number of children with no limit on foot performance in the main group was $61.6 \pm 5.8\%$ compared to the control group ($21.8 \pm 3.4\%$, $p \leq 0.05$). In the main group, the weight level of muscle hypotrophy (heel, calf) decreased by $68.5 \pm 7.2\%$ ($24.3 \pm 3.8\%$, $p \leq 0.05$) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Expression of disorders on neurological examination in the main group before and after treatment

Figure 3 Expression of movement disorders in neurological examination in the comparison group before and after treatment

The motion function without auxiliaries rose to $73.2 \pm 8.6\%$ in the main group and $42.3 \pm 4.4\%$ ($p \leq 0.05$) in the comparison group. The frequency of sharp disturbances decreased from $67.3 \pm 4.5\%$ in the main group to $13.8 \pm 2.4\%$ ($p \leq 0.05$), and $44.6 \pm 3.7\%$ ($p \leq 0.05$) in the comparison group. $65.7 \pm 7.6\%$ normalized ($P \leq 0.05$) in the control group ($34.4 \pm 4.7\%$, $p \leq 0.05$) compared to standing on the toes (comparison group). The ability to walk on the heel corresponds to $55.2 \pm 6.4\%$ in the main group and $29.6 \pm 4.7\%$ in the comparison group, with $p \leq 0.05$. The steppage (“cock walking”) intensity decreased from $45.8 \pm 4.9\%$ in the primary group to $10.3 \pm 2.4\%$ and was $21.6 \pm 4.3\%$ in the control group ($p \leq 0.05$).

Figure 4. Improvement in movement function detected in clinical and neurological examinations in children of the main group before and after treatment

Figure 5. Comparison before and after treatment improvement of movement function detected in clinical and neurological examinations in children in the group

3. 1. Improvement of treatment group after 45-day complex rehabilitation.

If there are 21 children with yatrogenic cause in diagnostics with Equinus installed on the leg before treatment (monoporesis as a result of an incorrectly performed intramuscular injection), after rehabilitation measures we noted that in almost all children the condition of the ankle has become normal. After all the rehabilitation (course of rehabilitation for 45 days), the pre-treatment scoliosis of children decreased, 90% of children returned to normal, indicating the high effectiveness of the rehabilitation we proposed [9]. However, when examined to assess the effectiveness of group-wide rehabilitation it was better to restore musculoskeletal functions in contrast to the severity of their Group I pathologies, with slightly improved Group II. In all patients, steppage, varus, recurvational deformities were present before treatment. After rehabilitation measures, including with the use of drug Ipigrix, a langeta link was installed to improve the functional condition of the joint [10]. Also damaged legs were corrected in the right position, with orthoses and orthopedic equipment. Orthopedic mode is set. After rehabilitation activities were conducted, leg varus deformity, joint sprains, recurvasia decreased by $89.4 \pm 5.6\%$ in children in the main group while ($56.7 \pm 4.3\%$, $R \leq 0.05$) in the control group. It was noted that a statistically significant back bend appears in the calf-heel joints at $67.3 \pm 4.6\%$ in the main group and $35.5 \pm 3.7\%$ in the comparison group ($r \leq 0.05$). The increase in Plantar flexor and scribal muscle strength was achieved at $93.6 \pm 5.4\%$ in the main group and $65.2 \pm 4.3\%$ ($R \leq 0.05$) in the comparison group. In the main group, the strength of the 1-finger lengthening muscles increased (in scores from 0 to 5) and was 5 points during rehabilitation, $83.5 \pm 4.4\%$ in the main group and $67.8 \pm 3.2\%$ in the control group. A very increase in muscle strength is more observed in proximal parts compared to distal, and the strength of the muscles of the legs is better restored, which is probably due to more pronounced pathological changes in the floor groups of the muscles of the legs [11, 12]. The patillary reflexes were restored on both sides (in the main group $6.8 \pm 3.7\%$ to $75.6 \pm 7.3\%$, comparison group $54.3 \pm 5.6\%$, $R \leq 0.05$); In the main group, plantar reflexes ranged from $6.8 \pm 3.7\%$ to $80.4 \pm 8.2\%$, compared to the comparison group of $49.8 \pm 4.3\%$ ($R \leq 0.05$); In the main group, the Achilles reflex ranged from 0.0% to $80.4 \pm 8.2\%$, in the comparison group $56.7\% \pm 5.1\%$ ($R \leq 0.05$). Joint-muscle sensitivity in the main group increased by $57.8 \pm 7.1\%$, while that of the comparison group was $24.5 \pm 3.7\%$. These indicators are explained by the complete or partial regeneration of afferent pathways under the influence of physical rehabilitation. As a result,

the rate of gait dependence from child-leading groups decreased from $23.5 \pm 4.6\%$ to $4.2 \pm 1.7\%$ in the primary group, and $6.7 \pm 2.1\%$ in the comparative group ($r \leq 0.05$) (Figure 6).

Figure 6. In the main group, reflex functions in the neurological examination before and after the treatmenting recovery changes.

Figure 7. Recovery changes of reflex functions in the neurological examination before and after treatment in the comparative group.

The index of vegetative synapses (Ashner test, Kerdo index) was noted to be $81.4 \pm 7.6\%$ in the primary group and $56.8 \pm 5.7\%$ ($R \leq 0.05$) in the comparison group.

An improvement in the main group after rehabilitation measures was found after 2-3 days, which was found to be reduced in leg neuropathy with swelling on the right side of the body (with $34.8 \pm 5.6\%$). In addition, the left leg tumor in the main group decreased by $45.8 \pm 4.7\%$ compared to the control group ($23.7 \pm 3.8\%$). The sensitivity on the right increased by $56.8 \pm 3.2\%$ in the main group and $21.4 \pm 4.1\%$ in the group under comparison. In the main group, the sensitivity level on the left decreased by $41.5 \pm 3.6\%$, and in the comparison-by $17.8 \pm 2.1\%$. In the main group, the night-time level of right-hand flutter decreased by $43.9 \pm 3.6\%$, and in the comparison group-by $23.8 \pm$

2.7%. In the main group, the night-time rubbing of the left side decreased by $43.2 \pm 3.6\%$, and in the comparison group-by $25.6 \pm 1.2\%$. Overall, the right-hand side's primary group flutter decreased by $45.6 \pm 5.2\%$, and the control group by $27.1 \pm 3.7\%$. It was found that the left-hand side rubbing in the main group decreased by $34.9 \pm 3.3\%$, and in the comparison group-by $13.6 \pm 1.8\%$ (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Clinical neurological changes after treatment in the main group.

Figure 9. Clinical neurological changes after treatment in the comparison group.

Analysis of data on Anamnesis showed that in 42.9% of patients in the comparison group, the duration of the disease is more than 1 year, 40% per year, 17.1% per month. In treating 82.9% of these cases, 74.3% of patients had low efficacy, 8.6% of patients had no significant effect, and 17.1% of patients did not receive full treatment.

After treatment, the comparison group observed movement restrictions in BDS at 4.14 times, muscle strengthening in the legs at 2.6 times, reactions to functional tests at 7 times and no changes

in reflexes, and a recovery of clinical and neurological indicators. Muscle strength and sensitivity in the legs increased [13].

The dynamics of subjective information in the main group is characterized by improvement in a reliable ($R < 0.05$) manner, shrinkage within the group, change in character, spread, reaction to trigger factors, movement restriction and decreased sensitivity disorders indicate the effectiveness of the taken measures.

After extensive rehabilitation in the main group, there was a decrease in movement restrictions in BDS by 6.6 times, an increase in muscle strength in the legs by 3.5 times, a decrease in response reactions to functional tests by 11.5 times, as well as a recovery in clinical and neurological indicators. Changes in reflexes, muscle strength and sensitivity in the legs were not observed [14].

The rate of neuropathy symptoms decreased by $46.8 \pm 7.4\%$, in the comparison group by $23.5 \pm 2.6\%$, in the leg neuropathy by $37.8\% \pm 3.0\%$, in the comparison group by $15.6 \pm 1.7\%$, as a result of improperly performed injections after the main group rehabilitation measures.

Figure 10. The frequency of occurrence of the main symptoms after rehabilitation measures in postinfective neuropathies in the main group.

Provocation tests were performed to confirm the diagnosis in all patients. Its results are in the figure 10 below.

A Phallen test was performed to diagnose postinfective mononeuropathies, with a positive test found in 44% of cases on the right ($p < 0.001$). Other positive provocation tests for the diagnosis of right – sided Foundry nerve neuropathy were found in 22.7% of children. Of the results obtained, a positive Tinel test was found in 5.3%, a positive elevation test in 6.7% and a positive Durkan test in 1.3% (Table 3).

Table 3. Foot neuropathy, provocation in patients with diabetes results of tests. (n=80)

Provocation tests	Results	Neuropathy of the legs, %
Phallena test on the right	Negative	100*
	Positive	0
Tinel test on the left	Positive	9,3**
Durkan test on the left	Positive	0

Froman test on the left	Positive	0
Elevation sinama on the left	Positive	0
Wartenberg test on the left	Positive	4,7

*-p <0,001, **-p <0,01.

Figure 11. Positive provocation tests in children frequency of occurrence

The detection of positive tests in leg neuropathy after rehabilitation events in the main group decreased by an average of $71.4 \pm 6.0\%$. Specifically, the Duncan test decreased to $80.8 \pm 3.5\%$, the Falen test to $35.7 \pm 4.1\%$, and the Elevation sinama to $51.2 \pm 4.8\%$.

4. Discussion

The performed correlation comparison analysis (row correlation coefficient of Spirmen) was based on the characteristic of the main neurological complaints for neuropathy of the legs (dysesthesia, paresthesias in the paws, rubs, pain in the direction of the nerve), age, BMI, dysesthesia (rubs) associated with pain in the leg joint (correlation coefficient 0.526), but pain in the thigh area (correlation coefficient 0.269) and weakly correlated with age (correlation coefficient 0.082). In particular, with a decrease in the correlation coefficient (0.360), (0.124 correlation coefficient) with a decrease in the correlation coefficient (0.360). The main clinical signs of pathology of the peripheral nervous system were analyzed for the presence of correlations between dysesthesia, pain in the joints of the legs and the age of the child). The clinical picture of peripheral neuropathy in observed patients has been dependent on the stage of the disease.

In the acute stage of the disease, spontaneous pain in the area of compression was observed in 71.2% of patients. Pain irradiation along the affected nerves is less common in the area of compression than local pain – at 40%. In 68.8% of our observation, pain was observed in nerve fibers damaged during palpation. Pain syndrome was manifested by burning, suppressive, sometimes acute attraction. The intensity of pain is greatest in neuropraxia of the nerve desks. Pain syndrome in the residual period was less severe than in the acute period, but it was much more stable and usually had more centralized characteristics. This was observed in 67.5% of cases in a clinical trial. At the same time, irradiating pain occurs more often-in-41.8% of cases. Nerve fiber pain affected during palpation was observed in 47.9% of cases. The pain syndrome was in the form of burns, stings and sprains. In almost all patients with peripheral neuropathy, damage to the sensory area was observed. Subjective sensitivity disorders were manifested in the form of paresthesias. At the same time, 72.9% of patients

were found to have occasional prick sensation, like “Ant walk” sniffing sensation, scrubbing in the innervation area of the affected nerve. In 7% of patients, there were difficulties in performing subtle targeted actions – “afferent paresis”. In addition to subjective manifestations of sensitivity disorders, an objective violation of pain sensitivity of the peripheral type was found in the form of hyperesthesia in the form of a less irritating feature and in the form of hypesthesia. Thus, in the acute stage of the disease, 64.2% of patients had pain sensitivity hypesthesia and 27.3% of patients had hyperesthesia. In the residual phase, patients experienced – 31.9% with descent type – 7.2% irritable type sensory disturbances. At the same time, disorders of the sensory area and differences in the basic pathogenetic form were not identified. Disorders expressed in patients in axonotmesis – 57.6% in Descent type (in neuropraxia cases – only 10.1%), and 39.9% in irritation type (with neuropraxia – 14.9%) were found. In the acute stage of the process, the effects of disorders in the area of motion were found in 72.3% of patients in the form of muscle paresis that innervate the affected nerves. The greatest, triple decrease in muscle strength was observed in 30% of patients. In 21.2% of patients, the less common muscle paresis was up to 4 points. Movement defects were noted in some patients: 0-1 points – 12.7% and 2 points – 15.8%. The frequency of occurrence of movement disorders in the chronic period of the disease is observed relatively a lot in the acute period – at 80.9%. However, the expression of the affected muscle paresis was slightly lower. In 10.3% of patients, acute movement disorders (inactivity) were found. In patients, paresis were rated at 41.7% -4 points, 14.9% -3 points, and 13.9% -2 points. The rule was more pronounced in cases of injury with partial axonal interruptions of movement disorders – the absence of movement in axonotmesis was in 44.9% of patients and 18.9% in neuropraxia. Normal tissue hypertrophy was observed in 28.6% of cases from trophic disorders. In the acute stage of the process, vegetative vasomotor disorders were most common: cyanosis, tumors in the distal sections of the legs, a decrease in temperature in the area where the affected nerve innervates. Dystrophic processes located in the innervation zone of damaged nerves during the residual period have caused dystrophic disorders such as skin trophic disorders, broken nails, hair loss, and osteoporosis. The extent of reflector disorders was to a large extent associated with nerve fiber damage. We have witnessed that 34.2% of patients with axonotmesis and 15.2% of patients with neuropraxia do not have reflexes. Hyperreflexia was found in some patients (5.4%) (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Children legs postinjective neuropathy rehabilitation effectiveness in movement disorders

Patients in the main group were patients who received scheduled complex medical rehabilitation treatments at RC for an average of 45-50 days.

Summarizing the data from the clinical and neurological examination of patients in the main group, these subjects have common characteristics: on average (77.1%) the prevalence of constant (22.9%) pain is mainly observed during movements, accompanied by daily loads, static stress and movement restriction in BDS. Data on Anamnesis showed that in 88.2% of cases, the disease is chronic. The objective examination revealed different levels of muscle tension in the legs, positive reactions to functional tests and restrictions on active movements.

After the patients in the main group were fully rehabilitated, a complete decrease in acute pain syndrome was noted, the average pain decreased by 78.9%, the constant decreased by 92.6%, the periodic decreased by 75%.

5. Conclusion

As for the conclusion, which summarizes the data obtained from the clinical and neurological examination of patients in the comparison group, it turned out that these subjects had common characteristics: moderate pain (65.7%) the prevalence of constant (71.4%) pain is mainly accompanied by movement during movements, daily loading, static stress and movement restriction in BDS. Data on Anamnesis showed that in 80% of cases, the disease is chronic and relapses more than twice a year in most patients. 60% of cases were associated with the effects of dynamic loading and 82.9% in cases where the degree of treatment was uncertain. An objective examination revealed different levels of muscle tension in the legs, positive reactions to functional tests and restrictions on active movements. In patients in the comparison group after treatment, the average acute pain decreased to 73.9%, persistent pain to 92% and periodic pain decreased to 60%.

IQTIBOSLAR | ЧОККИ | REFERENCES:

1. Asbery A. K. Diseases of the peripheral nervous system. // « Internal diseases». T. 10. – Moscow. – 2017.
2. Majidov N. M. , Mamadzhonov M. , Amasyants R. A. Clinic and treatment of diseases of the peripheral nervous system. Tashkent 2014.
3. Peripheral neuropathies: Report of the WHO research Group: Moscow 2012.
4. Sakharova A. V. , Lozhnikova S. M. , Pirogov V. N. , Piradov M. A. Expression of NADPH diaphorase in the peripheral nerve and its change at different stages of diphtheria polyneuropathy // Arkhiv Patologii 2019. – Vol. 61. – № 1.
5. Skripchenko N. V. Modern clinical and pathogenetic aspects of infectious diseases of the peripheral nervous system in children and principles of therapy. Moscow 2017.
6. Shamburov D. N. Infectious lesions of the peripheral nervous system // A multi-volume guide to neurology. Moscow, 2012.
7. Gorbunov F. E. , Strelkova N. I. , Vinnikov A. A. Pulse physiotherapy in rehabilitation of patients with motor disorders in peripheral myelinopathy and axonopathy // VII All-Russian Congress of Neurologists. Thesis – Nizhniy Novgorod, 2015.
8. Gruzman G. B. Electromyographic study of the blinking reflex in lesions of the peripheral nervous system// Journal of neuropathology. and a psychiatrist named after S. S. Korsakov. 2014.
9. Komantsev V. N. , Sorokina M. N. , Skripchenko N. V. Violation of excitability of the axon of the peripheral motor neuron in infectious lesions of the nervous system in children // XVII Congress of Physiologists of Russia. Rostov, 2018.
10. Mikhailov V. V. On the specificity of the cytopathogenic effect of diphtheria toxin in vitro// Successes of modern biology. 2014.
11. Nalimov V. V. Theory of experiment. Moscow. The science, 2015.
12. Panchenko D. N. The nature of diseases of nerve trunks // Questions of pathology of nerve trunks. Kyiv, 2016.
13. Персон Р. С. Электромиографическое исследование рефлекторных ответов и F – волны в клинике. Moscow 2013.
14. Roitbak A. I. Glia and its role in nervous activity. The science 2013.

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000